

Experimental / Localization

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API Version: 1.0.0

Provide spatio-temporal localization of the instances.

INDEX

1. COHORTS	3
1.1 GET /cohorts	3
1.2 PUT /cohorts	3
1.3 GET /cohorts/{guid}	4
1.4 DELETE /cohorts/{guid}	4
1.5 GET /localization/concrete/cohort/{guid}	5
2. INSTANCES	6
2.1 GET /instances	6
2.2 PUT /instances	6
2.3 GET /instances/{guid}	7
2.4 DELETE /instances/{guid}	7
2.5 GET /localization/concrete/instance/{guid}	8
2.6 POST /localization/concrete/instance/{guid}	9
2.7 POST /localization/logical/instance/{guid}	9
3. LOGICAL	11
3.1 GET /logical_locations/{guid}	11
3.2 GET /logical_locations	11
3.3 PUT /logical_locations	12
3.4 GET /localization/logical/instance/{guid}	12
3.5 POST /localization/logical/instance/{guid}	13
3.6 GET /localization/logical/cohort/{guid}	14

API

1. COHORTS

1.1 GET /cohorts

List Cohorts

List the GUIDs of the available cohorts.

REQUEST

No request parameters

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

[string]

1.2 PUT /cohorts

Put Cohort

Put a cohort based on its GUID.

REQUEST

REQUEST BODY - application/json

```
{  
  Represent a cohort of BIM instances.  
  url*      string  URL to the cohort data (e.g., in BIM Sync or BIM Extended)  
  guid*     string  PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_ . :- ]+$  
              generally unique identifier of the cohort  
  instances* [string]  
}
```

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  detail [{  
    Array of object:  
    loc* [string]  
    msg* string  
    type* string  
  }]  
}
```

1.3 GET /cohorts/{guid}

Get Cohort

Retrieve the cohort by the guid.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_-:~]+\$</code>	GUID of the cohort

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  Represent a cohort of BIM instances.  
  url*      string  URL to the cohort data (e.g., in BIM Sync or BIM Extended)  
  guid*     string  PATTERN: ^[a-zA-Z0-9_ . :- ]+$  
              generally unique identifier of the cohort  
  instances* [string]  
}
```

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  detail [{  
    Array of object:  
    loc*  [string]  
    msg*  string  
    type* string  
  }]  
}
```

1.4 DELETE /cohorts/{guid}

Delete Cohort

Delete the indicated cohort, or do nothing if it does not exist.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_-:~]+\$</code>	GUID of the cohort

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}
```

1.5 GET /localization/concrete/cohort/{guid}

Concrete Observations Of Cohort

Get all the location observations recorded for the cohort.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_-:~]+</code>	GUID of the cohort

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
[{
  Array of object: Observe something relative to the reference point of the site.
  coordinates* {
    Concrete coordinates
    x* number
    y* number
    z* number
  }
  timestamp* integer Time stamp when the location has been recorded (milliseconds since epoch in UTC)
}]
```

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}
```

2. INSTANCES

2.1 GET /instances

List Instances

List the identifiers of the available instances.

REQUEST

No request parameters

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

[string]

PATTERN: `^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$`

2.2 PUT /instances

Put Instance

Put an instance based on its GUID.

REQUEST

REQUEST BODY - application/json

```
{  
  Represent a track of a BIM instance.  
  guid*    string    PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$  
                Generally unique identifier of the instance  
  cohorts* [string]  
  url*     string    URL to the instance data (e.g., in BIM Sync or BIM Extended)  
}
```

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  detail [{  
    Array of object:  
    loc*  [string]  
    msg*  string  
    type* string  
  }]  
}
```

2.3 GET /instances/{guid}

Get Instance

Retrieve the instance by its GUID.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_-:~]+</code>	GUID of the instance

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  Represent a track of a BIM instance.  
  guid*   string   PATTERN: ^[a-zA-Z0-9_ . : - ]+$  
           Generally unique identifier of the instance  
  cohorts* [string]  
  url*    string   URL to the instance data (e.g., in BIM Sync or BIM Extended)  
}
```

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  detail [{  
    Array of object:  
    loc*   [string]  
    msg*   string  
    type*  string  
  }]  
}
```

2.4 DELETE /instances/{guid}

Delete Instance

Delete the indicated instance, or do nothing if it does not exist.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_-:~]+</code>	GUID of the instance

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}
```

2.5 GET /localization/concrete/instance/{guid}

Concrete Observations Of Instance

Get all the location observations recorded for the instance.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_-:~]+</code>	GUID of the instance

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
[{
  Array of object: Observe something relative to the reference point of the site.
  coordinates* {
    Concrete coordinates
    x* number
    y* number
    z* number
  }
  timestamp* integer Time stamp when the location has been recorded (milliseconds since epoch in UTC)
}]
```

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}
```

2.6 POST /localization/concrete/instance/{guid}

Post Concrete Observation Of Instance

Post a recorded location of an instance.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_-:~]+</code>	GUID of the instance

REQUEST BODY - application/json

```
{  
  Observe something relative to the reference point of the site.  
  coordinates* {  
    Concrete coordinates  
    x* number  
    y* number  
    z* number  
  }  
  timestamp* integer Time stamp when the location has been recorded (milliseconds since epoch in UTC)  
}
```

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  detail [{  
    Array of object:  
    loc* [string]  
    msg* string  
    type* string  
  }]  
}
```

2.7 POST /localization/logical/instance/{guid}

Post Logical Observation Of Instance

Post a recorded logical location of an instance.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_-:~]+</code>	GUID of the instance

REQUEST BODY - application/json

```
{
```

Represent an observation of a logical location for an instance.

```
  guid*      string  PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$  
                Globally unique identifier of the location  
  timestamp* integer  Time stamp when the location has been recorded (milliseconds since epoch in UTC)  
}
```

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  detail [{  
    Array of object:  
    loc*  [string]  
    msg*  string  
    type* string  
  }]  
}
```

3. LOGICAL

3.1 GET /logical_locations/{guid}

Get Logical Location

Retrieve the logical location by its GUID.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+\$</code>	GUID of the logical location

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  Represent a track of a BIM instance.  
  guid*   string   PATTERN: ^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$  
           Generally unique identifier of the instance  
  cohorts* [string]  
  url*    string   URL to the instance data (e.g., in BIM Sync or BIM Extended)  
}
```

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  detail [{  
    Array of object:  
    loc* [string]  
    msg* string  
    type* string  
  }]  
}
```

3.2 GET /logical_locations

List Logical Locations

List the available logical locations.

REQUEST

No request parameters

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
[{
```

Array of object: Represent a logical location.

This can be arbitrarily abstract and the location may not even exist in the physical world with a concrete spatial zone.

```
  guid* string PATTERN:[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$
           Generally unique identifier of the location
  url*  string URL to the location, e.g., in BIM Sync or BIM Extended
}]
```

3.3 PUT /logical_locations

Put Logical Location

Put a logical location based on its GUID.

REQUEST

REQUEST BODY - application/json

```
{
  Represent a logical location.
```

This can be arbitrarily abstract and the location may not even exist in the physical world with a concrete spatial zone.

```
  guid* string PATTERN:[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$
           Generally unique identifier of the location
  url*  string URL to the location, e.g., in BIM Sync or BIM Extended
}
```

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}
```

3.4 GET /localization/logical/instance/{guid}

Logical Observations Of Instance

Get all the logical locations recorded for the instance.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: [a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+\$	GUID of the instance

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
[{  
  Array of object: Represent an observation of a logical location for an instance.  
  guid*      string   PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$  
                Globally unique identifier of the location  
  timestamp* integer   Time stamp when the location has been recorded (milliseconds since epoch in UTC)  
}]
```

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  detail [{  
    Array of object:  
    loc*   [string]  
    msg*   string  
    type*  string  
  }]  
}
```

3.5 POST /localization/logical/instance/{guid}

Post Logical Observation Of Instance

Post a recorded logical location of an instance.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: ^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+\$	GUID of the instance

REQUEST BODY - application/json

```
{  
  Represent an observation of a logical location for an instance.  
  guid*      string   PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$  
                Globally unique identifier of the location  
  timestamp* integer   Time stamp when the location has been recorded (milliseconds since epoch in UTC)  
}
```

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  detail [{
```

Array of object:

```
loc* [string]
msg* string
type* string
}]
}
```

3.6 GET /localization/logical/cohort/{guid}

Logical Observations Of Cohort

Get all the logical locations recorded for the cohort.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+\$</code>	GUID of the cohort

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
[{
  Array of object: Represent an observation of a logical location for an instance.
  guid*      string    PATTERN: ^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$
                                     Globally unique identifier of the location
  timestamp* integer    Time stamp when the location has been recorded (milliseconds since epoch in UTC)
}]
```

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
    loc* [string]
    msg* string
    type* string
  }]
}
```
